

A Study of the Maternal Complications and Outcomes in Patients with Eclampsia in a Tertiary Care Centre, Assam

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Received: 25-04-2024 / Revised: 23-05-2024 / Accepted: 26-06-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Background: Eclampsia is the convulsive manifestation of the hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and is among the more severe manifestations of the disease. It is derived from a Greek word meaning “like a flash of lightning”. Hypertensive disorders of pregnancy contribute to 14% maternal deaths globally. Eclampsia is one of the leading causes of intensive care unit (ICU) admission. The maternal complications and outcomes were studied in this study.

Methods: The present study was a hospital based descriptive study conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh. The duration of study was 1 year with effect from 1st May 2023 to 30th April, 2024. The study comprised of all patients who fulfilled the inclusion exclusion criteria and gave written and informed consent and details were recorded in a predesigned proforma.

Results: The incidence of eclampsia was 2.4%. The major complications developed in 55% eclamptic patients in our study. These were pulmonary oedema (47.27%), hematuria (23.64%), ARF (14.55%), elevated liver enzymes (40%), electrolyte imbalance (21.82%), DIC (7.27%), abruptio (7.27%), cardiomyopathy (5.45%), CVA (1.82%), HELLP (5.45%) and fever in 14.55% cases. 12.73% were admitted to ICU and 14.55% cases died. The leading cause of death was pulmonary oedema (100%) followed by AKI (62.5%), MODS (62.5%) and aspiration pneumonitis (12.5%).

Conclusion: Prevention of eclampsia can be done by regular antenatal care, early recognition of warning signs and its prompt treatment. Health awareness, improvement in literacy status, upliftment of socioeconomic conditions, and healthcare services play an important role in reduction in incidence of eclampsia and its complications.

Keywords: Eclampsia, Maternal Complications.

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Introduction

Eclampsia is the convulsive manifestation of the hypertensive disorders of pregnancy and is among the more severe manifestations of the disease. Eclampsia is defined by new-onset tonic-clonic, focal, or multifocal seizures in the absence of other causes. It is derived from a Greek word meaning “like a flash of lightning” [5]. The earliest historical documentation of eclampsia comes from Hippocrates, who noted that headache, seizures and altered consciousness were ominous signs seen in some pregnancies [6]. The term eclampsia first appeared in the Varandaeus treatise on gynaecology [7]. According to WHO, eclampsia develops in 2.3% of the preeclamptic women in the developing world compared with 0.8% of preeclampsia cases in developed country [8]. A number of factors are responsible for difference in incidence of preeclampsia in developed and

developing nations. These factors include routine antenatal care, early detection of preeclampsia, timely delivery and the availability of healthcare facility. Young primi gravidas are most commonly affected and those with minimum and skipped antenatal care [9]. Eclampsia is most common in the third trimester near term [10]. Maternal outcome includes severe morbidities such as pulmonary edema, renal failure, coagulopathy, cardiac failure, HELLP, hepatic failure, cerebrovascular accidents, increased rates of instrumental deliveries and caesarean sections. Fetal outcome includes prematurity, intrauterine growth restriction, meconium aspiration syndrome, birth asphyxia, intraventricular haemorrhage. Many drugs have been used for the treatment of eclampsia. Among all the anticonvulsant drugs used, Magnesium Sulfate has been found to be

effective. The only definitive treatment for eclampsia is termination of pregnancy. Considering the high rate of prevalence of eclampsia in our locality and high maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity associated with it and lack of any similar studies in the past, we have carried out this prospective study to assess the maternal complications and outcomes in patients with eclampsia.

Materials and Methods

This study was conducted in the Department of Obstetrics and Gynaecology, Assam Medical College and Hospital, Dibrugarh from May, 2023 to April, 2024.

Inclusion criteria

- All patients with antepartum eclampsia.
- Gestational age more than 20 weeks.
- Postpartum eclampsia cases were included if convulsions occurred within 7 days of delivery.

Exclusion criteria

- Gestational age less than 20 weeks.
- Women who were known cases of epilepsy, seizures due to metabolic disturbances, space occupying lesions, cerebral arterial ischemia and infarction, intracranial hemorrhage or drug use.

Results

Table 1: Age wise Distribution

Age Group (in years)	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
≤20	17	17.00
21–25	52	52.00
26–30	22	22.00
>30	9	9.00
TOTAL	100	100.00
Mean ± S.D.	24.37 ± 4.14 years	

In this study, the minimum age was found to be 19 years and maximum age was 35 years. The mean age was 24.37 ± 4.14 years. Out of 100 eclamptic women, 17% of the women were below 20 years of age, 52% were between 21-25 years of age and 22% belonged to the age group between 26-30 years. 9% women were above 30 years of age.

Figure 1: Age wise Distribution

Table 2: Parity wise Distribution

Parity	Number (n)	Percentage (%)
Primigravida	53	53.00
Multigravida		

• P1	17	17.00
• P2	15	15.00
• ≥P3	15	15.00
Total	100	100.00

Out of 100 patients enrolled for the study, 53% patients in the study population were found to be Primigravida and 47% were multigravida out of which 17 were primipara, 15 were para2 and 15 were para3 or more.

Figure 2: Parity wise Distribution

Table 3: Booked/Unbooked

Booked/Unbooked	Number (N)	Percentage (%)
Booked	35	35.00
Unbooked	65	65.00
Total	100	100.00

Out of 100 patients, 35% were booked cases and 65% were unbooked cases.

Table 4: Complications of Eclampsia

Complications	Number (n=55)	Percentage (%)
Pulmonary oedema	26	47.27
Hematuria	13	23.64
Acute Renal Failure	8	14.55
Elevated Liver Enzymes	22	40.00
Electrolyte Imbalance	12	21.82
DIC	4	7.27
Abruptio Placenta	4	7.27
Cardiomyopathy	3	5.45
Cerebrovascular Accidents	1	1.82
HELLP	3	5.45
Fever	8	14.55
ICU Admission	7	12.73
Death	8	14.55

Figure 3: Complications of Eclampsia

In our study, 55 patients developed complications. Out of the 55 patients, 47.27% patients developed pulmonary oedema, 23.64% hematuria, 14.55% had AKI, liver enzymes were elevated in 40%, 21.82% had electrolyte imbalance, DIC developed in 7.27%, 7.27% had abruptio, 5.45% cardiomyopathy, 5.45% developed HELLP, 14.55%

had temperature of more than 100 degrees Fahrenheit.

The total number of ICU admissions was 12.73%. Among those who developed complications, 14.55% died.

Table 5: Complications present in expired patients

Complications	Number (n = 8)	Percentage (%)
Pulmonary Oedema	8	100.00
AKI	5	62.50
MODS	5	62.50
Aspiration Pneumonitis	1	12.50

Figure 4: Complications present in expired patients (n = 8)

Total 8 eclampsia patients died due to complications. Among them, 8(100%) developed pulmonary edema and died, 5(62.5%) died due to AKI, 5(62.5%) had MODS and 1(12.5%) died due to aspiration pneumonitis.

Discussion

Eclampsia is one of the severe manifestations of hypertensive disorders of pregnancy. From our studies, the incidence of eclampsia was 2.4% which is similar to other studies by Indian authors, though the incidence is much less in developed countries. Babita Kapoor et al in her studies in 2016 reported an incidence of 4% [11].

In our study, 20 patients did not have any prior antenatal check-up anywhere. 9 patients had only single antenatal check-up either in AMCH or in other peripheral centres. 38 patients had 2 antenatal check-ups till date of admission and 33 cases had 3 or more antenatal check-ups. Only 10 patients had regular antenatal check-ups in AMCH. 35% were booked cases and 65% were un-booked cases. ShaheenB. et al. in 2008 in their study found 88% cases were not booked [12].

In another study by Babita Kapoor and colleagues (2015-2016), 35.5% did not receive any antenatal care [13]. 17% of the women in our study were below 20 years of age, 52% were between 21-25 years of age and 22% belonged to the age group between 26-30 years. 9% women were above 30 years of age. Biswas Et al. (2005) reported from his series 41.43% cases were below 20 years of age

[14]. The incidence of eclampsia was more in primigravida. 53% patients were Primigravida while only 47% were multigravida. In most of the studies, the incidence has been found to be higher in primigravida patients. Shaheen B et al. in 2008 found 48.8% incidence in primigravida [15]. The major complications developed in 55 eclamptic patients in our study.

These were pulmonary oedema (47.27%), hematuria (23.64%), ARF (14.55%), elevated liver enzymes (40%), electrolyte imbalance (21.82%), DIC (7.27%), abruptio (7.27%), cardiomyopathy (5.45%), CVA (1.82%), HELLP (5.45%) and fever in 14.55% cases. 12.73% were admitted to ICU and 14.55% cases died. Maria Khannum (2004) found 16% patients developed pulmonary oedema, 1% ARF, 3% CVA and 2% died [16]. In studies by Sunita Mor et al. in 2015, 6% developed HELLP and 4% died [17]. In our studies out of 55 patients who developed complications, 8(14.55%) of them died. The leading cause of death was pulmonary oedema (100%) followed by AKI (62.5%), MODS (62.5%) and aspiration pneumonitis (12.5%). This can be compared with Study conducted by Aparna Khan et al. (2014) who reported that 40% mothers died of cerebral hemorrhage, 28% mothers died of pulmonary edema, one mother died of aspiration, one mother due to septicemia and one died due to acute renal failure [18]. Studies by Ratan Das et al. (2015) also showed pulmonary edema to be the leading cause of death in eclampsia patients [19].

Conclusion

Eclampsia is one of the major causes of maternal mortality and morbidity in India. The mortality rates are higher due to poor socioeconomic conditions, lack of awareness, illiteracy and lesser accessibility to healthcare services. Prevention of eclampsia can be done by regular antenatal care, early recognition of warning signs and its prompt treatment. Timely referral of the patients with eclampsia to the nearest tertiary care institution can significantly reduce maternal and perinatal mortality and morbidity. Health awareness, improvement in literacy status, upliftment of socioeconomic conditions, and healthcare services play an important role in reduction in incidence of eclampsia and its complications.

References

1. Hossain MA, Karmoker RK, Rahman MS, Rashid HO, Khan SH, Rahman MA. Comparison of Outcome of Eclamptic Patient Following Vaginal Delivery versus Caesarian Delivery by Spinal Anaesthesia. *Mymensingh Med J.* 2018 Apr; 27(2):275-279.
2. Say et al., Global Causes of Maternal Death.
3. Vousden et al., Incidence of Eclampsia and Related Complications across 10 Low- and Middle-Resource Geographical Regions.
4. Lam and Dierking, Intensive Care Unit Issues in Eclampsia and HELLP Syndrome.
5. Hossain MA, Karmoker RK, Rahman MS, Rashid HO, Khan SH, Rahman MA. Comparison of Outcome of Eclamptic Patient Following Vaginal Delivery versus Caesarian Delivery by Spinal Anaesthesia. *Mymensingh Med J.* 2018 Apr; 27(2):275-279.
6. J Chadwick, WN Mann - 1950 - 117.239.25.194.
7. Salas, What Causes Pre-Eclampsia?
8. F. Gary Cunningham, Kenneth J. Leveno, Jodi S. Dashe, Barbara L. Hoffman, Catherine Y. Spong, Brian M. Casey, *Williams Obstetrics*, 26e.
9. Swain et al., Maternal and Perinatal Mortality Due to Eclampsia.
10. F. Gary Cunningham, Kenneth J. Leveno, Jodi S. Dashe, Barbara L. Hoffman, Catherine Y. Spong, Brian M. Casey, *Williams Obstetrics*, 26e.
11. Kapoor, Verma, and Shrivastava, Role of Antenatal Care in Reducing Incidence of Eclampsia in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India.
12. Shaheen, Hassan, and Obaid, Eclampsia, a Major Cause of Maternal and Perinatal Mortality.
13. Kapoor, Verma, and Shrivastava, Role of Antenatal Care in Reducing Incidence of Eclampsia in Eastern Uttar Pradesh, India.
14. Das and Biswas, Eclapmsia.
15. Shaheen, Hassan, and Obaid, Eclampsia, a Major Cause of Maternal and Perinatal Mortality.
16. Marina K, Fatema A, Humaira S. A Clinical Study of 100 Cases of Eclampsia in Rajshahi Medical College Hospital. *TAJ.* 2004, 17(2): 80-83.
17. Mor, Sirohiwal, and Hooda, Eclampsia.
18. Khan, Aparna et al. Analysis of the Causes of Maternal Death in Eclampsia. *IOSR Journal of Dental and Medical Sciences* 13 2014; 07-10.
19. Das and Biswas, Eclapmsia.